

**Autonomous learning behaviors in an online coding community:
A comparison between project viewing/playing and code remixing in
Scratch using Benford's Law**

Ray Y. Shen

21 **Reviewer's comments:**

22 *I enjoyed reading your paper but still there always is a room for improvement. I do not wish*
23 *to point out much but still what I found is that while your study offers profound insights into*
24 *the Scratch community, it would be beneficial to discuss how these findings might translate to*
25 *other online learning communities or coding platforms. Comparative analysis with other*
26 *platforms could strengthen the generalizability of your results. Incorporating qualitative*
27 *data, such as user interviews or surveys, could provide a richer understanding of the*
28 *motivations behind viewing, playing, and remixing behaviors. This would complement the*
29 *quantitative analysis and offer a more holistic view of user engagement.*

30 *Overall, your paper is a significant contribution to the field of educational technology and*
31 *online learning communities. I appreciate the depth of your analysis and the practical*
32 *implications of your work. I look forward to seeing more research in this area and how your*
33 *findings might influence the design of online learning environments.*

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35 **Author's response:**

36 Many thanks again for the reviewer's evaluation of the manuscript and the very
37 helpful and encouraging comments. The manuscript has been further revised based on these
38 suggestions. In the Discussion section, we have addressed the potential translation of our
39 findings to other environments. We have also included a discussion on the benefits of
40 integrating the quantitative Benford analysis with qualitative data to enhance our
41 understanding of the motivations behind autonomous code learning activities. Additionally,
42 we have highlighted the potential applications of this work in the Abstract section. A minor
43 overall improvement of the manuscript has also been made. The two newly added paragraphs
44 in Discussion are as follows:

45 "In addition to the quantitative Benford analysis described here, incorporating
46 qualitative data from users' comments is expected to provide a richer, more nuanced
47 understanding of autonomous learning behaviors on the Scratch platform. Users often share a
48 variety of insights in the Scratch comments section, including specific aspects of the projects
49 they found engaging, innovative, or enjoyable. These comments can reveal users' emotional
50 responses, preferences, and the educational value they perceive in the projects, offering

51 important context and depth to the numerical data. By examining these comments, we can
52 better understand why certain projects are more popular, shedding light on user preferences
53 and the impact of specific project attributes. Furthermore, comments may include feedback
54 on learning outcomes, such as how users apply the knowledge gained from others' projects to
55 their own coding activities. Integrating these qualitative insights with the quantitative leading
56 digit distributions can provide a more comprehensive view of user engagement, linking the
57 observed Benford statistics to the underlying motivations behind autonomous code-learning
58 behaviors.

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60 Finally, the Benford analysis highlighted in this study can be applied to other online
61 coding platforms such as GitHub and online learning environments other than computer
62 programming. Outside of Scratch, other sources of qualitative data, particularly interviews,
63 have already proven to be highly useful for gaining a deeper understanding of online coding
64 communities (Dabbish et al., 2012). By analyzing qualitative data, educators can identify
65 recurring themes and motivations that drive engagement, such as features that particularly
66 resonate with students or elements of online educational platforms that foster learning.
67 Therefore, combining quantitative Benford analysis with conventional student engagement
68 metrics including qualitative data, for example, from student surveys and interviews is
69 expected to be a fruitful approach to broadening our understanding of online learning
70 activities beyond the Scratch community. This approach will not only enhance the
71 interpretation of statistical analyses, including leading digit distributions, but also inform the
72 design of various educational platforms to facilitate more effective and engaging learning
73 experiences on a variety of educational platforms.”

76 **Autonomous learning behaviors in an online coding community:**
77 **A comparison between project viewing/playing and code remixing**
78 **in Scratch using Benford’s Law**

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81 **Abstract:**

82 Previous studies of code-learning behaviors have been conducted in structured educational
83 settings, utilizing student engagement metrics such as homework submission, task completion,
84 and interactions with instructors. These types of metrics, however, are absent in open online
85 coding platforms. To characterize autonomous code-learning behaviors in an online community,
86 this work applied Benford’s Law to analyze user engagement metrics of trending projects on
87 Scratch, the world’s largest online coding platform for young learners. Statistical analysis
88 revealed that the extent of conformity to Benford’s Law is independent of the project categories.
89 Of all four user engagement metrics, the views metric exhibited the strongest conformity to
90 Benford’s Law, while the remixes metric—the metric most closely associated with code-learning
91 behaviors—showed the greatest deviation from Benford’s Law. This was confirmed by Pearson’s
92 χ^2 test, Nigrini’s mean absolute deviation test, and an evaluation of the mantissas of the user
93 engagement metrics. This study demonstrates that the extent of conformity to Benford’s Law can
94 be used as novel features for characterizing autonomous code-learning behaviors in unsupervised
95 online settings. The results of this work pave the way for future studies to correlate the extent of
96 conformity to Benford’s Law with specific elements of code that attract autonomous learning,
97 providing opportunities to optimize the content and design of online coding platforms.

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99 **Keywords:** computer science education, computational thinking skills, code-learning behaviors,
100 data mining, Benford’s Law.

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103 **INTRODUCTION**

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106 Previously, studies on code-learning behaviors have been conducted in classroom settings or instructor-
107 led online environments, where conventional student engagement metrics are assessed. For example, Chen et al.
108 (2020) used machine learning to study the code-learning behaviors of 69 students enrolled in a Java
109 programming course, analyzing engagement metrics like homework effort (e.g., number of specific failures,
110 number of on-time submissions, and total submissions) and homework time (e.g., time to first submission, time
111 to last submission, and duration in a specific state of failures). Stewart et al. (2021) examined the code-learning
112 behaviors of ten middle school female students enrolled in a virtual coding camp using engagement metrics such

113 as responses to prompts via chat, student presentations, and code-sharing. Sun et al. (2021) studied two
114 instructional modes for teaching coding to 31 students—instructor-directed lecturing and learner-centered
115 unplugged programming—using classroom audio and video recordings, student surveys, and interviews to
116 assess code-learning behavioral patterns. Alebaikan et al. (2022) studied the online code-learning experience of
117 16 female middle schoolers, generating data from interviews, the teacher’s diary, and content analysis of
118 activities recorded in student progress reports. While many studies have utilized conventional student
119 engagement metrics—such as attendance, help-seeking, homework submission, task completion, interactions
120 with instructors, and logs of various study activities—to study code-learning behaviors in well-structured
121 educational settings, these types of metrics are absent in unsupervised online coding platforms, where millions
122 of users engage in autonomous learning. In contrast to the numerous studies of student code-learning behaviors
123 in formal educational settings, to the best of our knowledge, there have been no parallel investigations of
124 autonomous learning behaviors in online coding communities.

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126 Benford’s Law, also known as the first-digit law or the law of anomalous numbers, describes a
127 common statistical phenomenon in the distribution of leading digits of many naturally occurring datasets. First
128 discovered by Simon Newcomb (1881) and later popularized by Frank Benford (1938), the first-digit law can be
129 used to analyze population sizes, stock values, scientific measurements, and tax records (Nigrini, 2012, p. 25).
130 The law’s fundamental principle dictates that in many non-synthetic datasets, a leading digit of “1” appears
131 significantly more frequently than any other digit, at an expected 30.1% frequency. The expected frequency of
132 occurrence decreases as the leading digit increases, to 17.6% for “2” as a leading digit and down to an expected
133 mere 4.6% appearance rate for “9” as a leading digit (Benford, 1938). Benford’s Law can provide insights into
134 unexpected patterns, anomalies, or even fraud that a dataset might contain based on conformity of the data. The
135 first-digit law’s numerous applications include assessing the quality of synthetic images without the need for
136 any reference images (Varga, 2021), identifying dynamic transitions in cardiac models (Seenivasan, et al.,
137 2016), and evaluating the conformity of cancer registry data to expected patterns (Crocetti & Randi, 2016). Of
138 particular interest, the extent of conformity to Benford’s Law has recently been used as novel features to train
139 artificial intelligence models (for example, Caffarini et al., 2022). Considering the large amount of datasets on
140 learning behaviors already accumulated by educators and researchers, applying Benford’s Law to study learning
141 behaviors could uncover new insights and potentially enhance educational practices.

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143 Due to the vast amounts of data voluntarily provided by its users, social media contains many
144 opportunities for studying trends in data, user tendencies, and human behaviors. Datasets created from user
145 interactions on popular social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, or TikTok can be used by
146 researchers to track shifts in internet trends, monitor changes in public opinion over various topics, or analyze
147 internet culture (Felt, 2016). Social media data is also useful in studying the impact of the spreading of
148 information, political discourse, and the dynamics of various online communities (Abkenar et al., 2021). Many
149 datasets gathered from mainstream social media conform to Benford’s Law, and those that don’t could suggest
150 unknown or unexpected user behaviors, data irregularities, or manipulation. The distributions of different user
151 engagement metrics, such as views or reposts, have been found to closely follow Benford’s Law, and can
152 therefore be used to discern patterns. Datasets mined from mainstream social media can both be validated or

153 discredited by making statistical comparisons to the expected distribution derived from Benford’s Law (e.g.,
154 Bhosale & Troia, 2022).

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156 Scratch (<https://scratch.mit.edu>) is a visual programming language and online coding platform designed
157 to introduce programming concepts to young learners, with over 120 million registered users and more than 150
158 million published projects. Developed by the Lifelong Kindergarten Group at the MIT Media Lab, Scratch
159 provides a user-friendly environment for creating various projects such as games, animations, and stories.
160 Scratch’s intuitive visual interface, drag-and-drop code blocks, and simple tutorials appeal to young learners, as
161 the need for traditional text-based programming is eliminated. Acting as an integrated coding and social media
162 platform, Scratch encourages its users to publish their projects, remix the creations of others, leave comments,
163 and interact with the online community. While social media data has proven valuable for understanding student
164 learning (Su & Lai, 2021) and studies have used Scratch to teach computational thinking to small groups in
165 classroom settings (e.g., Kwon et al., 2018; Kwon & Cheon, 2019; Erumit & Sahin, 2020), online coding
166 communities, including Scratch, have not yet been studied and analyzed utilizing data mining and data analytic
167 techniques to extract valuable statistics related to the social interactions and autonomous learning behaviors of
168 their users.

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170 To address these gaps, this work takes the first steps in investigating the vast amount of social
171 interaction and engagement data on Scratch by collecting and examining the projects featured on its trending
172 page to extract statistical information on user engagement metrics in terms of their conformity to Benford’s
173 Law. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to investigate learning behaviors using Benford’s Law.
174 Our study unequivocally demonstrates that while the views metric of Scratch, like similar metrics in mainstream
175 social media, obeys Benford’s Law, the remixes metric, which involves active coding, deviates dramatically
176 from this law. These findings indicate that the extent of conformity to Benford’s Law can serve as a highly
177 sensitive measure for characterizing code-learning in a social network dominated by autonomous learning
178 activities, where conventional user engagement metrics are non-existent. Further studies can, for example,
179 correlate the extent of conformity to Benford’s Law with the level of computational thinking skills exhibited in
180 Scratch projects. These lines of research are expected to offer additional insights into specific elements in
181 Scratch code that attract autonomous learning. Such insights could potentially lead to the optimization of online
182 coding platforms, benefiting both autonomous learning within online communities and instructor-led learning in
183 educational settings that utilizes popular programming interfaces such as Scratch.

186 METHODS

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189 *Benford’s Law*
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Let D_i be the i th digit of an arbitrary number n . Benford's Law denotes that for every positive integer $k \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \sim \{1\}$, all $d_1 \in \{1, 2, 3 \dots, 9\}$ and all $d_j \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, 9\}$ with $j \in \{2, 3, 4, \dots, k\}$, the probability of n naturally occurring with its first k significant digits given by d_1, \dots, d_k is (Nigrini, 2012, p. 13):

$$P(D_1 = d_1, \dots, D_k = d_k) = \log_{10}(1 + (\sum_{i=1}^k d_i * 10^{k-i})^{-1}) \quad [1]$$

Note that since $k \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \sim \{1\}$, we can calculate the probability of a specific leading digit by summing the probabilities of all numbers starting with that digit in Equation [1] (Benford, 1938):

$$P(d) = \log_{10}(1 + \frac{1}{d}) \quad [2]$$

where d is the leading digit.

Data collection and analysis

Scratch's trending page consists of six project categories: Animations, Art, Games, Music, Tutorials and Stories. Each Scratch project has four user engagement metrics: loves, favorites, remixes and views. Users can browse through projects in each category and interact with them by viewing/playing the projects and leaving loves and favorites. Users are also able to remix a project, where they can customize, add to, or fully revamp another user's project and republish it as their own while automatically crediting the original author. In contrast to views, loves, and favorites, the remixing metric is associated with active coding.

This work utilizes Google's free web scraping tool, Web Scraper (<https://webscraper.io>), to automatically extract the counts of all user engagement metrics of each trending project from all six project categories and exports them to Microsoft Excel files. The data collection does not require ethical approval since the information is freely available in the public domain. The Web Scraper, which was installed as a Chrome Extension, had over 600,000 users as of 2023. We utilized a recursive pagination handler that allows verification of successful data collection by comparing the last scraped records with those on the initial pages. The selector graph used for data collection in this study is provided in the appendix (Figure S1).

While Pearson's chi-square (χ^2) test (Bock et al., 2019, p. 621) is the go-to test when comparing an experimental distribution with a theoretical one and some authors are still using it to test conformity to Benford's Law, its limitations are well-documented due to its over-sensitivity to minor fluctuation in digits when the size of the dataset is large (Nigrini, 2012, p. 158), such as in the current study. To overcome this limitation, the Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD) test has been developed and widely accepted for testing conformity to Benford's Law (e.g., Nigrini, 2012, p. 158; da Silva et al., 2020; Azevedo et al., 2021). Additionally, we used the strong Benford's Law (Berger & Twelves, 2018), which applies to the entire number rather than only its leading digit, to address the limitation of focusing solely on leading digits.

Let O_i represent the observed occurrence of leading digit i , let N represent the total number of records, and let P_i represent the frequency of the occurrence of leading digit i expected from Benford's Law. The standardized residual of a leading digit can be found by subtracting the expected occurrence from the observed occurrence and dividing the difference by the square root of the expected occurrence (Bock et al., 2019, p. 624):

$$\text{Standardized Residual} = \frac{O_i - NP_i}{\sqrt{NP_i}} \quad [3]$$

Pearson's chi-square statistic, denoted by χ^2 , is found by summing the squared standardized residuals between observed and expected occurrences (Equation [3]) for all leading digits 1 through 9 (Bock et al., 2019, p. 621):

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^9 \frac{(O_i - NP_i)^2}{NP_i} \quad [4]$$

While null hypothesis significance tests, such as Pearson's chi-square test, are prone to oversensitivity to insignificant spikes with large sample sizes, the MAD test is independent of the sample size and is known for its well-tested ability to assess conformity to Benford's Law (Nigrini, 2012, p. 158). The MAD score can be calculated by taking the average of the absolute values of the differences between the observed frequency and expected frequency from Benford's Law for each leading digit 1 through 9 (Nigrini, 2012, p. 158):

$$MAD = \frac{1}{9} \sum_{i=1}^9 \frac{|O_i - NP_i|}{N} \quad [5]$$

For the theoretical Benford distribution, the MAD score is zero. A higher MAD score for a distribution of leading digits indicates greater deviation from Benford's Law, and vice versa. The ranges of critical MAD scores for conformity to Benford's Law, as described by Nigrini (2012, p. 160), are as follows: 0-0.006 for close conformity, 0.006-0.012 for acceptable conformity, 0.012-0.015 for marginally acceptable conformity, and > 0.015 for nonconformity.

All data analysis was performed using computer programs written in Python 3.12 with the following imported libraries: os, pandas, matplotlib, math, numpy, scipy.stats, seaborn, and scikit_posthocs. The nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by Dunn's post-hoc test, was employed to compare MAD scores across both different project categories and different user engagement metrics.

RESULTS

Data mining located 1,285 projects from the Animations category, 6,431 from the Art category, 2,536 from the Games category, 2,315 from the Music category, 2,138 from the Tutorials category, and 6,768 from the Stories category. The successful project data retrieval rates ranged from 99.5% to 100% for all six categories

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and all sample sizes in the study are well above the sample sizes used in many studies regarding Benford behavior (e.g., Drucia et al., 2018).

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Figure 1. First digit distributions of the user engagement metrics in the Animations category. (A) Loves; (B) Favorites; (C) Remixes; (D) Views. Green bars represent the observed percentage frequencies of leading digits, while the red circles depict the percentage frequencies of leading digits predicted by Benford’s Law.

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We first assess the extent of conformity to Benford’s Law by the four user engagement metrics in all project categories. The distribution of the percentage frequencies of leading digits for the Animations project category as well as the theoretical Benford distribution (Equation [2]) are shown in Figure 1. The percentage frequencies of leading digits for all six project categories are given in Table 1. Rather than a uniform distribution of leading digits, the datasets exhibit Benford-like behavior via a trend of decreasing percentage frequencies from a leading digit of 1 to 9 as displayed in Figure 1 and Table 1. Shown in Table 2 are the results of Pearson’s chi-square test and the mean absolute deviation test, performed to categorize levels of conformity to Benford’s Law for each user engagement metric under all six project categories. Standardized residuals for Pearson’s chi-square test (Equation [3]) are provided in the appendix (Table S1).

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Table 1. Percentage frequencies for each leading digit

Category	User Engagement	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
	Loves	29.56	20.20	14.59	9.20	8.35	5.54	5.07	3.51	3.98

Animations	Favorites	32.06	19.65	14.32	10.34	7.64	5.09	4.14	3.50	3.26
	Remixes	53.72	19.42	10.55	5.04	3.12	2.88	2.64	1.44	1.20
	Views	32.06	17.78	11.47	8.66	7.49	6.79	7.10	4.29	4.37
Art	Loves	26.82	19.17	15.61	10.73	8.66	6.76	4.98	4.31	2.95
	Favorites	31.55	22.62	14.85	9.44	6.51	5.06	4.45	3.15	2.36
	Remixes	56.56	15.95	8.71	5.46	3.46	2.94	3.67	1.89	1.36
	Views	32.90	16.67	10.96	8.55	7.40	6.59	5.91	5.77	5.24
Games	Loves	32.78	23.37	13.52	9.37	6.56	4.98	3.99	3.08	2.33
	Favorites	34.37	23.96	13.18	8.90	6.78	4.33	3.31	2.86	2.33
	Remixes	51.77	19.11	8.73	6.58	3.80	3.54	2.28	2.28	1.90
	Views	29.27	18.60	12.12	9.12	7.50	6.67	6.24	5.77	4.70
Music	Loves	26.65	18.33	15.51	11.09	8.71	6.28	5.55	4.12	3.77
	Favorites	27.10	20.50	15.61	10.90	8.70	6.55	4.80	3.14	2.69
	Remixes	50.14	17.99	11.05	6.09	4.25	2.83	2.97	2.69	1.98
	Views	30.36	17.37	12.21	9.74	6.89	6.19	6.97	6.15	4.11
Tutorials	Loves	48.67	20.61	10.63	6.51	4.45	3.00	3.00	1.83	1.31
	Favorites	49.79	20.97	10.43	6.68	3.60	3.03	2.47	1.75	1.28
	Remixes	64.67	15.27	9.28	3.29	2.99	1.80	2.10	0.30	0.30
	Views	34.05	18.48	12.25	8.89	7.20	5.75	4.72	4.68	3.98
Stories	Loves	45.76	18.29	11.06	7.70	5.12	3.56	3.64	2.71	2.17
	Favorites	45.26	18.97	11.53	6.97	5.29	4.15	2.84	2.51	2.48
	Remixes	51.10	16.75	10.31	5.86	5.03	3.22	3.87	2.13	1.74
	Views	33.16	18.37	12.93	9.20	7.02	6.22	5.40	4.21	3.49

The results listed in Table 2 indicate a strong negative correlation between the P values from Pearson’s chi-square test (Equation [4]) and the MAD scores (Equation [5]). The results of Table 2 also confirm the observation made by Nigrini and others (Nigrini, 2012, p. 153) that Pearson’s chi-square test can be overly sensitive for large sample sizes, such as the ones in this study. Consequently, for assessing differences in conformity to Benford’s Law across the six project categories and the four user engagement metrics, only the MAD test results are utilized. To compare Benfordness across different project categories, the MAD scores of the four user engagement metrics of each project category were averaged. Figure 2(A) compares the mean MAD scores of the Animations, Art, Games, Music, Tutorials, and Stories project categories using a box plot, with each box in the plot representing a distinct project category. The Kruskal-Wallis test on the six groups of MAD scores outputs a Kruskal-Wallis statistic of 3.1 and a P-value of 0.68, demonstrating that there is no statistically significant difference in Benfordness across the different project categories. The test concludes that rather than being category-specific, the extent of conformity to Benford’s Law follows a similar pattern for all six project categories.

Table 2. Goodness-of-fit tests

Category	User Engagement	Pearson’s χ^2 Test		MAD Test	
		χ^2	P	MAD Score	Conformity
Animations	Loves	21.3	6.3×10^{-3}	1.1×10^{-2}	a.c.
	Favorites	30.6	1.7×10^{-4}	1.4×10^{-2}	m.a.c
	Remixes	138.4	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	5.6×10^{-2}	n.c.

	Views	10.0	2.6×10^{-1}	7.7×10^{-3}	a.c.
Art	Loves	146.3	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	1.5×10^{-2}	m.a.c.
	Favorites	285.7	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	2.0×10^{-2}	n.c.
	Remixes	343.9	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	5.9×10^{-2}	n.c.
	Views	54.6	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	9.3×10^{-3}	a.c.
Games	Loves	135.4	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	2.1×10^{-2}	n.c.
	Favorites	175.8	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	2.5×10^{-2}	n.c.
	Remixes	211.4	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	5.2×10^{-2}	n.c.
	Views	6.7	5.7×10^{-1}	4.9×10^{-3}	c.c.
Music	Loves	41.8	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	1.3×10^{-2}	m.a.c.
	Favorites	77.9	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	1.8×10^{-2}	n.c.
	Remixes	160.8	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	4.5×10^{-2}	n.c.
	Views	15.6	4.8×10^{-2}	5.6×10^{-3}	c.c.
Tutorials	Loves	483.3	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	4.9×10^{-2}	n.c.
	Favorites	499.3	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	5.2×10^{-2}	n.c.
	Remixes	209.1	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	7.6×10^{-2}	n.c.
	Views	24.5	1.9×10^{-3}	1.1×10^{-2}	a.c.
Stories	Loves	931.5	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	3.6×10^{-2}	n.c.
	Favorites	870.0	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	3.7×10^{-2}	n.c.
	Remixes	366.0	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	4.7×10^{-2}	n.c.
	Views	64.9	$<1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	9.3×10^{-3}	a.c.

a.c.: acceptable conformity; c.c.: close conformity; m.a.c.: marginally acceptable conformity; n.c.: nonconformity.

Next, we test whether different user engagement metrics averaged across different project categories demonstrate statistically different levels of conformity to Benford’s Law since loves, favorites, remixes, and views exhibit varying degrees of association with learning behaviors. As shown in Table 2, the views metric consistently has the largest P-values across all project categories. The P-values for the views of the Animations and Games project categories are well above the commonly used significance level of 0.05, despite Pearson’s chi-square test being overly stringent for our purpose. Table 2 indicates that for all project categories, the views metric falls into the close conformity or acceptable conformity range by the MAD test. However, for the remaining loves, favorites, and remixes metrics, adherence to Benford’s Law mostly falls into the nonconformity range. In particular, all remixes metrics lie in the nonconformity range. Only the favorites metric for the Animations category and the loves metric for the Art and Music categories are placed in the marginally acceptable conformity range, while the loves metric for the Animations category was the only non-views metric categorized into the acceptable conformity range, as shown in Table 2. For comparing conformity to Benford’s Law across different user engagement metrics, the MAD score of each user engagement metric averaged over the six project categories was computed. The comparison is shown in Figure 2(B) via another box plot. The Kruskal-Wallis test on the four groups of user engagement metrics generated a Kruskal-Wallis statistic of 18.1 and a P-value of 0.00042, indicating statistically significant differences among the mean MAD scores of the user engagement metrics. When comparing loves with favorites, loves with remixes, loves with views, favorites with remixes, favorites with views, and remixes with views, Dunn’s post-hoc test yielded the following P-values: 0.668, 0.032, 0.037, 0.086, 0.012, and 0.000024, respectively. The loves-favorites comparison indicated

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the least difference in conformity to Benford’s Law while the remixes-views comparison indicated the greatest difference.

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Figure 2. Box plots depicting the MAD scores across different project categories (A) and different user engagement metrics (B).

Lastly, we examine the density distributions of the mantissas of the logarithms of the user engagement metrics, as the stringent form of Benford’s Law requires uniformity in the fractional part of the logarithms of a dataset (Berger & Twelves, 2018). This stronger form of Benford’s Law is fundamental and more rigorous than Equation [2]. Displayed in Figure 3 are the density distributions for the Animations project category. Note the large difference in uniformity between the densities of the mantissas of the views and remixes metrics shown in Figure 3. The standard deviations of the binned densities for the mantissas for the Animations category are 6.1%, 6.9%, 14.5%, and 1.5% for loves, favorites, remixes, and views, respectively. The density distributions of the mantissas for all project categories are listed in Table 3. All six project categories follow the same general pattern for the standard deviations of the densities of the mantissas: views < loves < favorites < remixes. This pattern corroborates results presented in Table 2 and Figure 2(B).

Figure 3. Density distributions for the mantissas of the logarithms of different user engagement metrics in the Animations category. (A) Loves; (B) Favorites; (C) Remixes; (D) Views.

Table 3. Standard deviations of densities (%) for mantissas of the logarithms

Category	User Engagement	Standard Deviations
Animations	Loves	6.1
	Favorites	6.9
	Remixes	14.5
	Views	1.5
Art	Loves	6.3
	Favorites	8.4
	Remixes	15.0
	Views	2.0
Games	Loves	8.2
	Favorites	9.0
	Remixes	13.9
	Views	2.1
Music	Loves	5.5
	Favorites	6.6
	Remixes	13.6
	Views	1.3
Tutorials	Loves	13.9
	Favorites	14.3
	Remixes	18.9
	Views	5.3
Stories	Loves	11.1
	Favorites	11.3
	Remixes	12.7

DISCUSSION

Though many studies have been conducted on user interaction data mined from mainstream social media platforms, to the best of our knowledge, this work is the first to extract and analyze user engagement metrics of an online coding community, Scratch, which combines both social and learning components. This work found that while all views metrics closely conform to Benford's Law, approximately 58% of user engagement metrics across the six project categories were categorized into the non-conformity range with a MAD score above 0.015. It was determined that there is no statistically significant difference in Benfordness when comparing the six project categories (Kruskal-Wallis P-value = 0.68 \gg 0.05; also see Figure 2(A)), but a great distinction among user engagement metrics averaged across the six project categories was found (Kruskal-Wallis P-value = 0.00042 \ll 0.05; also see Figure 2(B)).

One potential influence on these results can be attributed to Scratch's unique role as both a code-learning platform and a form of social media for young learners. A Scratch user may run a project as many times as they like, contributing to multiple recorded views on the project despite them all from one unique viewer. The total view counts of a project are the result of multiplying the number of viewers by the number of views per viewer, and as explained by Scott and Fasli (2001), mathematically, datasets adhere more closely to Benford's Law when they are formed by multiplying two or more independent variables. Therefore, it is not surprising that the views metrics of all six project categories were found to both consistently and closely adhere to Benford's Law. Although a Scratch user can view a project multiple times, projects are limited to at most one recorded love or favorite per user. As a result, the mechanism of enhancing Benfordness via the multiplication effect is not applicable to the loves and favorites metrics.

As previously stated, the remixes user engagement metric stands out from the other three as it is the metric most strongly associated with the code-learning behaviors of Scratchers. Mainstream social media platforms have components similar to Scratch's views, loves, and favorites metrics but do not have any features resembling the ability to remix projects. When a Scratch user plans to remix a project, they may have to study the project in-depth to understand where and how they can modify the project and add their own code. This technical experience offers valuable insights into programming logic, design principles, and problem-solving techniques, especially if the original project is complex. Unlike viewing and playing, remixing a project is associated with active code learning, often going beyond any built-in Scratch tutorials and more advanced online guides. By building upon existing projects, a user can experiment with new ideas, functionalities, and designs that are difficult to create without a template. Interestingly, the data shows that the remixes metric deviates the furthest from Benford's Law, indicated by the chi-square and MAD tests (see Table 2 and Fig 2), as well as the standard deviations of the mantissas of the user engagement metrics (see Table 3 and Fig 3).

401 Other than the project-level user engagement metrics analyzed in this work, additional sources of
402 information at the user level on the Scratch website could be studied, including follower count, following count,
403 number of comments, and age of users. Scratch also has many other features, such as project studios where users
404 can collaborate to build a collage of projects with a common theme or purpose. Additionally, Scratch has
405 featured project groups aside from the trending page, such as the “What the Community is Loving” section and
406 the “What the Community is Remixing” section which could be analyzed for Benford behavior. Data on these
407 other features could be gathered and studied through data mining to provide further insights into peer
408 interactions and learning experiences of Scratch users. Scratch also offers a comment section under each project,
409 which can be analyzed using techniques such as natural language processing.
410

411 A straightforward extension of the current study to most online coding platforms is currently not
412 feasible. For example, SNAP! (<https://snap.berkeley.edu/>) is closely modeled after Scratch and provides a very
413 similar coding platform. It offers users options to view, embed, and download the code of published projects.
414 But SNAP! does not report any user engagement data. There are no counts of views, loves, favorites, or remixes
415 for any projects on SNAP!. Like Scratch, Thinkable (<https://thinkable.com/solutions/education/>) also uses a
416 drag-and-drop coding environment, allowing learners to build video games by adding various components such
417 as buttons, images, and voices, thus turning a passive online experience into an engaging educational one.
418 However, Thinkable does not publish any user projects. Code.org offers a diverse array of instructional courses
419 for teachers and students alike, with over 210 million projects created on the platform. However, like SNAP!,
420 Code.org does not provide any user engagement metrics (<https://studio.code.org/projects/public>). On the other
421 hand, GitHub provides public counts of stars and forks, akin to favorites and remixes in Scratch. However, no
422 Benford analysis has been conducted on GitHub. In light of the numerous recent efforts in studying code-
423 learning behaviors, it would be greatly beneficial for all educational coding platforms to provide user
424 engagement data as these data can provide considerable insights to autonomous code-learning behaviors in
425 online communities. Understanding these autonomous learning behaviors has many potential benefits, such as
426 informing improved content and platform design, thereby aiding millions of online learners.
427

428 Although this study is limited to the projects featured on the trending page of Scratch (N = 21,473), the
429 strategy used in this study can be extended to the entirety of Scratch. In particular, computational thinking skills,
430 defined by abstraction and problem decomposition, logical thinking, synchronization, parallelism, algorithmic
431 notions of flow control, user interactivity, and data representation, can be quantified (Moreno-León et al., 2019)
432 and correlated with the extent of conformity to (or deviation from) Benford’s Law by user engagement metrics.
433 The extent of conformity to Benford’s Law, in turn, can be used to gauge the development of computational
434 thinking skills in an open online coding environment with peer support networks such as Scratch. A related
435 study of academic publishing networks using Benford’s Law has been reported recently (Tošić & Vičič, 2021).
436 Such studies may not only provide insights into the effectiveness of online platform design features but also
437 offer opportunities for optimizing code-teaching strategies. As Benford’s Law is being applied to an ever-
438 increasing array of diverse research areas, from detecting weak seismic signals (Díaz et al., 2015) to analyzing
439 complex networks including social media networks (Morzy et al., 2016), the extent of conformity to Benford’s
440 Law, including the complex patterns of mantissas of user engagement metrics as exemplified by Fig 3, may also

441 serve as novel features in artificial intelligence models to study social interactions and autonomous learning
442 behaviors in online coding communities.

443
444 In addition to the quantitative Benford analysis described here, incorporating qualitative data from
445 users' comments is expected to provide a richer, more nuanced understanding of autonomous learning behaviors
446 on the Scratch platform. Users often share a variety of insights in the Scratch comments section, including
447 specific aspects of the projects they found engaging, innovative, or enjoyable. These comments can reveal users'
448 emotional responses, preferences, and the educational value they perceive in the projects, offering important
449 context and depth to the numerical data. By examining these comments, we can better understand why certain
450 projects are more popular, shedding light on user preferences and the impact of specific project attributes.
451 Furthermore, comments may include feedback on learning outcomes, such as how users apply the knowledge
452 gained from others' projects to their own coding activities. Integrating these qualitative insights with the
453 quantitative leading digit distributions can provide a more comprehensive view of user engagement, linking the
454 observed Benford statistics to the underlying motivations behind autonomous code-learning behaviors.

455
456 Finally, the Benford analysis highlighted in this study can be applied to other online coding platforms
457 such as GitHub and online learning environments other than computer programming. Outside of Scratch, other
458 sources of qualitative data, particularly interviews, have already proven to be highly useful for gaining a deeper
459 understanding of online coding communities (Dabbish et al., 2012). By analyzing qualitative data, educators can
460 identify recurring themes and motivations that drive engagement, such as features that particularly resonate with
461 students or elements of online educational platforms that foster learning. Therefore, combining quantitative
462 Benford analysis with conventional student engagement metrics including qualitative data, for example, from
463 student surveys and interviews is expected to be a fruitful approach to broadening our understanding of online
464 learning activities beyond the Scratch community. This approach will not only enhance the interpretation of
465 statistical analyses, including leading digit distributions, but also inform the design of various educational
466 platforms to facilitate more effective and engaging learning experiences on a variety of educational platforms.

469 Conclusion

470
471
472 Our study using Benford's Law revealed a highly significant difference between project
473 viewing/playing and code remixing in the online Scratch community. This distinction in conformity to
474 Benford's Law is validated by multiple independent statistical analyses. Given that the extent of conformity to
475 Benford's Law has been utilized in various artificial intelligence applications (e.g., Caffarini et al., 2022; Hsu &
476 Berisha, 2022), and artificial intelligence has been employed to study code-learning behaviors in supervised
477 settings (e.g., Lin et al., 2024), our findings suggest that combining Benford's Law and artificial intelligence
478 presents a promising approach to advancing our understanding of autonomous code-learning behaviors and peer
479 interactions in open online coding communities. These avenues of research are anticipated to foster new

opportunities for optimizing the content and design of online coding platforms to benefit millions of users engaged in autonomous learning.

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APPENDIX

Figure S1. Selector graph for recursive pagination. The filled circles indicate nodes for recursive extension of the algorithmic paths.

Table S1. Standardized residuals of each leading digit from Pearson’s χ^2 test

Category	User Engagement	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Animations	Loves	-0.35	2.21	2.12	-0.56	0.54	-1.60	-1.08	-2.54	-1.00
	Favorites	1.26	1.72	1.83	0.74	-0.35	-2.20	-2.45	-2.53	-2.18
	Remixes	8.79	0.88	-1.12	-3.05	-3.48	-3.01	-2.68	-3.32	-3.22
	Views	1.28	0.15	-1.04	-1.19	-0.55	0.13	1.93	-1.31	-0.35
Art	Loves	-4.79	2.99	7.07	2.67	2.12	0.22	-2.74	-2.86	-6.08
	Favorites	2.05	9.27	5.18	-0.62	-3.89	-4.90	-4.35	-6.73	-8.05
	Remixes	14.89	-1.22	-3.31	-4.20	-4.89	-4.48	-2.73	-4.40	-4.63
	Views	4.09	-1.80	-3.47	-2.93	-1.47	-0.31	0.37	2.32	2.49
Games	Loves	2.45	6.90	1.46	-0.52	-2.42	-3.33	-3.77	-4.52	-5.27
	Favorites	3.85	7.49	0.97	-1.26	-2.01	-4.53	-5.12	-4.94	-5.20
	Remixes	11.10	1.01	-2.99	-2.81	-4.12	-3.42	-4.11	-3.53	-3.52
	Views	-0.77	1.19	-0.53	-0.92	-0.74	-0.04	0.92	1.45	0.29
Music	Loves	-3.03	0.82	4.10	2.16	1.35	-0.77	-0.51	-2.12	-1.81
	Favorites	-2.59	3.26	4.17	1.84	1.32	-0.26	-1.96	-4.12	-4.16
	Remixes	9.70	0.24	-1.09	-3.07	-3.46	-3.97	-3.12	-2.85	-3.22
	Views	0.22	-0.28	-0.38	0.08	-1.76	-0.93	2.34	2.20	-1.04
Tutorials	Loves	15.63	3.30	-2.43	-4.72	-5.70	-6.60	-5.38	-6.72	-7.05
	Favorites	15.83	3.53	-2.57	-4.27	-6.77	-6.24	-6.10	-6.57	-6.79
	Remixes	11.51	-1.02	-1.66	-3.76	-3.20	-3.46	-2.81	-3.89	-3.65
	Views	3.33	0.95	-0.31	-1.19	-1.18	-1.68	-2.06	-0.90	-1.30
Stories	Loves	22.94	1.30	-3.26	-5.13	-7.99	-9.75	-7.22	-8.56	-9.06
	Favorites	21.62	2.54	-2.14	-6.84	-7.31	-7.71	-9.61	-9.00	-7.66
	Remixes	15.07	-0.80	-2.43	-4.84	-4.05	-5.29	-3.16	-5.21	-5.22
	Views	4.57	1.50	1.01	-1.29	-2.62	-1.51	-1.35	-3.27	-4.18